

Prevention of contact corrosion in hybrid laminates by knitted spacing structure

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Keywords

contact corrosion, hybrid laminates, knitted spacing structure, electrical resistance measurement on FRP, thermal forming of thermoplastics

Abstract

To research the influence of a contact corrosion prevention layer, a testing plate out of a hybrid material setup is produced. Therefore, metal sheets (steel and aluminium) were combined with a thermosetting carbon fibre reinforced plastic. In-between the area of potential contact corrosion, a knitted structure was integrated and compared to an additional included film layer and a reference without a preventing layer. To research the influence of forming processes to the separation layer, the specimens were bend, before further preparations, as like to remove overlapping carbon fibre material and applying a conductive paste, were done. The function of the separation was proven by measuring the resistance of the specimens through the setup, by contacting the carbon fibre and the metal material. The investigation shows, that the knitted separation layer withstands the manufacturing process, but isn't able to prevent the banding-caused contact of the carbon fibre and the metal material.

1 Introduction

When it comes to lightweight design, fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) are a common way to combine the characteristics of a fibre-material and a matrix, for achieving a high stiffness and strength in combination with a low weight. A step further, hybrid material tries to combine different beneficial material characteristics to achieve even better mechanical and structural properties, as like higher elongation at breaking or even joining with classical techniques. [1] but the combination of specific materials can course problems. In the case of a combination of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) and aluminium

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alloy, under certain conditions the effect of contact corrosion occurs. [2] This happens, if electrically conducting fibre material, in combination with a conductive liquid, gets in contact with the aluminium alloy. [3] The corrosion, for example happens, if single fibre ending stick out of the surface of CFRPs or after fibre cracking during of shaping or bending processes of hybrid material. To avoid the contact of the two materials, by building a physical barrier, an additional layer has been integrated into the setup of the hybrid laminate.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Preperation of the corrosion preventing layer

Avoiding the contact forced corrosion of the aluminium alloy, a spacing structure is integrated in the joining area of the corresponding materials. Therefor a knitted structure was chosen by its beneficial characteristics of a high structural elongation at breaking and its abability of adapting to complex three dimensional geometries. Specific textile characteristics are needed to successfully use such a layer into a multi-material compound. Reducing the influence of the textile structure in regard to the handling and forming process, as well as the mechanical properties of the hybrid material, a drape-able, nearly closed fabric with a low area weight is convenient. Therefore, a knitted structure out of an aramid yarn has been produced (Figure 1). As yarn a aradmid with a yarn count 100 Nm was choosen. The textile structure was made by the help of a flatbed knitting mashine CMS 502 HP from Stoll. To achieve a specific distance between the problematic materials, two yarns have been processed at the same time for realising a defined volume as barrier layer. With this technic a area weight of 109 g/m² was produced.

Figure 1: Knitted textile structure (left); close up (right)

In the next step, to reduce the lag of matrix material and avoiding the enclosure of defects, the knit has been embedded into a PA12 film Grilamid L XE 10953 from EMS-Grivory. Additionally the film have the funktion of overcoming the problem of athision, caused by the passivating oxid-layer form the aluminium, and additionally to increased bond between the joining pratners. The integration of the knitted textile structure was done by a hot prssing process, were the knit was fixed under specific pre tention, stackt up with two 75 µm film and heat pressed at 220 °C for 10 minutes.

2.2 Hybrid material assambly

For testing the effect of the produced corrosion preventing layer, it was embedded into a stack between a sheet of aluminium alloy AW 6082 or a Steel sheet in combination with an FRP-sheet, consisting out of carbon fibre, a Polyamide 6 matrix and glass fibre for cost-saving. Several options, with and without the preventing layer and a layer just by the PA 12 film, are build. Stacks with the prevention layer and the film were build up in a way, that the knitted layer (or film) separates the metal material and the carbon fibre, the glass fibre was laid up at the outer face. A thermal press process was used for joining the hybrid material. After heating up the stack for 8 minutes within a contact oven at 280 °C and 6 bar, the thermosetting material was transferred in addition with the aluminium sheet into a thermal press process.

Within this process, the material stays for 3 minutes at 160 °C under a load of 250 kN, before it was extracted.

From the plan testing plate (Figure 2 left), smaller specimens were extracted, to investigate the influence of a forming process in regard to the separation characteristics of the corrosion preventing layer. To simulate the influence of a bending or forming process, the specimens are deformed in a thermal bending process by the help of a U-shaped tool (figure 2 right).

Figure 2: testing plate (left); formed specimens (right)

2.3 Speciment preperarion

Right from this process, all specimens has got some overlapping carbon fibre material, that's been removed before further treatments. The material were cleaned by the use of a cutter knife and sanding of the edges, avoiding the direct contact of the fibre material and the metal material in these areas.

To electrically contact the carbon fibre of the hybrid material, the outer layer (glass fibre) was removed locally by the use of a grinder and sanding paper with a 240 grid. After cleaning these areas with acetone, to remove dust and residues, an electrical silver based conductive paste was applied directly to the carbon fibre and cure for 24 hours. To contact a specific area, not a single fibre, an area of 1 cm² was masked by tape, that's been removed before curing.

3 Results

A necessary boundary condition for the effect of contact corrosion is a physical connection between the metal component and the electrically conductive fibre endings. Carbon fibre, as well as metal material, has got the characteristic of a low specific electrical resistance. By separating the two materials from each other and measure the resistants by contacting two electrodes to each material, leads to a high resistants. This effect is used to research the effectivity of the preventing layer.

The measurements were done under usage of mechanical clamps as electrodes, to avoid a change in resistants through compaction of the fibres or accidentally contacting the materials by supplanting of the matrix material. One clamp has been attached to the metal sheet and the other to the prepares area of the fibre material. In comparison, the measurements were done within a curved, as well as a non-bend specimen. The results of the measurements are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Example

Material	Separation Layer	Condition	Resistents in Ω
Steel	Knitt	Flat	2.700.000
Steel	Knit	Bended	12

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Material	Separation Layer	Condition	Resistents in Ω
Steel	Film	Flat	4
Steel	Film	Bended	4
Steel	Non	Flat	1
Steel	Non	Bended	23
Aluminium	Knitt	Flat	1711
Aluminium	Knitt	Bended	10
Aluminium	Film	Flat	7
Aluminium	Film	Bended	16
Aluminum	Non	Bended	28

4 Discussion and conclusion

The manufacturing process shows, in general, that the combination of the chosen material is convenient. It is possible to integrate a knitted spacing structure within the stack, by joining with thermal pressing processes. It also can be seen, that the material can be formed, by the help of thermal treatment to enable the thermosetting matrix material to flow.

The results of the resistant measurement shows a huge overall variation of the electrical resistants. Especially the specimens with the spacing layer, independent of the metal material, reached a high value of resistants in flat condition. In comparison, the film-based competitor got a low resistance, as well as the non-spacing reference. The reduction of resistants at the aluminium-film-variant is caused by a supplanting of the film material within the described thermal pressing processes. After the thermal treatment the fibre material gets in contact with the metal material, which can cause contact corrosion.

In comparison to that, the bended specimens all has got a low value of resistants, independent of the material combination. While the bending process, matrix material was pushed out of the areas from the edges, which causes a contact of fibre material with the metal material. This also happens with the knitted spacing structure. Within these areas fibers an able to push through the knitted structure and cause an electrical flow, which leads to contact corrosion.

This leads to the point, that the separating layer in general works, except for forming processes. Further research can be done by investigating the influence of the thickness of the knitted corrosion preventing layer, in regard to the influence of the additional layer to the mechanical properties of the hybrid material. As well as the dependence of forming radiuses in regard to the protecting characteristic of the knitted spacing layer.

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